

CHANGES OF MECHANICAL PROPERTIES AND STRUCTURE OF PA 6 COMPOSITES FILLED BY GLASS FIBER UNDER DYNAMICAL LOADING

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SUMMARY

The results of properties and structure investigation of PA 6 composites filled by glass fiber under cyclic loading were presented. Changes of elasticity modulus, strain and dissipated energy under different values of cyclic load as well as SEM images on different stages of fatigue were compared.

Keywords: polyamide 6, glass fibre, mechanical properties, structure, cyclic loading.

INTRODUCTION

The composites on the base of thermoplastic polymers are used widely in many technical applications substituting traditional materials and giving a new technological and a constructional opportunities. It results from its good mechanical properties, low density, easy making of products, corrosion resistance, easy processing and recycling compared to composites on the base on thermosets. The process of spreading their use needs to be proceeding by investigations of their properties and include the conditions of exploitation and limitations connected with it. In case of applications which are expect to work reliable for long time, the problem of changing properties under static and dynamic load as well as environment (temperature, moisture) occurs. The way and intensity of decreasing properties of material become key issue, especially under conditions of cyclic loading. The knowledge about dependence between structure of the composite and other properties (e.g. mechanical) can result in preparing composites with better applied properties [1, 2, 3].

The aim of this work was to estimate the influence of cyclic loading on changes of mechanical properties and structure of polyamide composites which are widely used in technical applications. Additionally influence of an injection molding temperature on basic mechanical properties was estimated.

EXPERIMENTAL PART

Material

The composites were prepared on the based on PA 6 produced by Zakłady Azotowe in Tarnow, Poland (trade name Tarnamid T-27). Tarnamid T-27 has mean molecular weight and is designed for injection molding and modification by mixing. As the filler there was

used short glass fiber (diameter about 10 μm , an average length about 150 μm). A granulate was prepared by compounding on extrusion line with two-screw extruder. Components of the composite were mixed with addition improving miscibility and increasing adhesion between the matrix and the fiber. Before the injection, the granulate was dried in temperature 80°C by to 4 hours, up to moisture content of the level 0,2%. The specimens were prepared by the injection molding in three rising temperatures for certain composite (PA 6 with 25% GS – injection temperature 260, 270 and 280°C, PA 6 with 50% GS – injection temperature 280, 290 and 300°C; form temperature 80-100°C, velocity 90 mm/s, pressure 90 MPa) from PA6 with 25 and 50% of glass fiber weight content. Considering ability to absorb water by PA 6, the specimens used in dynamical tests were conditioned in natural conditions by three months in room temperature. For pure PA 6, the content of moisture was 1,8 %, for PA 6 with 25% of glass fiber – 1,2 % and for PA 6 with 50% of glass fiber – 0,6%.

Methods

The tensile tests were carried out for the composites at 21°C and 65 % RH using an automatic tensile tester (Instron type 4465) according to PN-EN ISO 527. A modulus of elasticity, a tensile strength and a strain at break was obtained.

The measurement of the water content was carried out according to PN-81/C-89032 for specimens' dimensions 4x10x100 mm by measuring the mass before and after wetting.

The melt flow index was measured according to PN-EN ISO 1133:2002, the temperature was 230°C and the load 21,6 N.

The properties under a dynamic loading were tested on the dynamical machine in tensile test (Instron type 8511.20) on the level of frequency - 5 Hz for maximum 100 000 cycles ("load-unload"). The cyclic loading was within the range 0,1 - 0,5 of average maximum force reached in the tensile test – for content of glass fiber 25% $P_{\text{max}}=5,2$ kN, for content of glass fiber 50% $P_{\text{max}}=7,9$ kN (tab. 2). The computer program was created to convert a numerical data from a tensile machine and calculate mechanical properties including a modulus of elasticity, an elongation, a creep effects and a mechanical energy of dissipation during sequence of the hysteresis loops.

The scanning electron microscope (SEM) used was a Joel JSM 5510LV (low vacuum). The tensile fracture surfaces and cyro-fractured surfaces (generated by breaking the specimen under liquid nitrogen conditions) were studied.

Results and discussion

The basic mechanical properties obtained in tensile test for dry and wet specimens were presented in table 1. Adding glass fiber caused increase of modulus from about 3 200 MPa for pure PA 6 to 15 000 MPa with addition of 50% of glass fiber, tensile strength increased from 60 to average 197 MPa - 50% GF (for dry specimens). Changing temperature of injection molding in given range didn't influence on basic mechanical properties. The values differ in range of method error. The content of water for tested specimens was shown in Fig. 1. Adding glass fiber influences on decreasing absorption of water from the level of 11% for pure PA 6 to the level of 3,8% for PA 6 with 50% of glass fiber (about three month of wetting).

Influence of injection molding temperature on MFI was shown in Fig. 2. Increase the temperature of injection molding caused increasing the value of measured MFI which can effect on lower value of molecular weight of composite as a result of faster cooling specimen in injection form. Additionally special preparation of glass fibers caused

increase of MFI value for composite with 50% glass fiber compared to composite with 25% glass fiber. It is the advantage in case of injection thin-walled details.

Table 1. The basic mechanical properties obtained for the tested composites.

glass fiber content, % weight/temperature of injection, °C	Modulus of elasticity [MPa]		Tensile strength [MPa]	
	<i>dry</i>	<i>wet</i>	<i>dry</i>	<i>wet</i>
PA0/240	3200	890	63	31
PA0/260	3350	920	64	31
PA0/280	3650	950	67	32
PA25/260	7270	3870	122	65
PA25/270	7540	3630	134	67
PA25/280	7470	3950	133	70
PA50/280	15280	9050	196	102
PA50/290	15860	8530	200	110
PA50/300	15800	8720	197	112

glass fiber content, % weight/temperature of injection, °C	Strain at P_{max} [%]		Energy [J]	
	<i>dry</i>	<i>wet</i>	<i>dry</i>	<i>wet</i>
PA0/240	3.7	280	0.65	0.11
PA0/260	3.5	280	0.57	0.10
PA0/280	3.1	300	0.55	0.11
PA25/260	3.3	7	1.07	0.28
PA25/270	3.2	7	1.56	0.34
PA25/280	3.2	8	1.53	0.31
PA50/280	2.9	4.5	1.64	0.38
PA50/290	2.9	5.0	1.74	0.47
PA50/300	2.9	5.0	1.46	0.46

Figure 1. The absorption of water for the tested composites.

Figure 2. The melt flow index for the tested composites, injected in three temperatures (load $P = 21.6 \text{ N}$, temperature 230°C).

In table 2, the average number of loading cycles for tested specimens and number of loading cycles before fracture was shown. The maximal number of load cycles was 100 000 and in case of lower value of load ($0,4$ and $0,45 P_{\max}$) the specimens didn't fracture.

Table 2. The average number of the loading cycles for the tested composites for different levels of force.

glass fiber content, % weight	Level of force from $0,1 P_{\max}$ to	P_{\max} in cycle [kN]	The average number of cycle
25	$0,40 P_{\max}$	2,08	100 000
	$0,45 P_{\max}$	2,34	100 000
	$0,50 P_{\max}$	2,60	$88\ 000 \pm 1\ 000$ - fracture
	$0,55 P_{\max}$	2,86	$6\ 000 \pm 300$ - fracture
50	$0,40 P_{\max}$	3,10	100 000
	$0,45 P_{\max}$	3,35	100 000
	$0,50 P_{\max}$	3,95	$10\ 000 \pm 450$ - fracture

Exemplary hysteresis loops registered during the tests for PA 6 with 25% of glass fibers and for two levels of load are shown in Fig. 3. We can observe the change of position (gradient angle) and increase of surface of first loop compared to last one under cyclic loading which influence on the value of modulus of elasticity and dissipated energy. The modulus of elasticity characterizes linear decrease under cyclic loading, and before fracture of specimen it rapidly decreases. The decrease of elasticity modulus is the most significant in case of stress value leading to fracture (Fig. 4). Additionally we can observe that the decrease of elasticity modulus under cyclic loading is more intensive for composites with 50% of glass fiber. The influence of increase of load is in this case more evident. The higher weight content of fiber in composite may increase the probability of fiber fracture and decrease border number of cycles leading to failure of material. The value of fatigue stress is higher because of higher value of maximal load and tensile strength of composite with 50% of glass fiber.

Figure 3. The hysteresis loops for PA with 25% glass fiber for two levels of force (comparison of first and last cycle for each load)

Figure 4. The modulus of elasticity under cyclic loading: PA6 with 25% glass fibre (left side), PA6 with 50% of glass fibre (right side).

The dissipation of energy and elongation increase under cyclic loading and similarly to modulus of elasticity, the changes are the most significant for upper levels of load (Fig. 5-8). In Fig. 4, the SEM images of fractured surfaces on different stages of fatigue of material were presented. We can observe the change of fracture character from brittle at the beginning of test (about 1000 cycles of load) to ductile at the end and loss of an adhesion between the matrix and the fibre.

Figure 5. The dissipated energy in the function of number of cycles for PA 6 with 25% glass fiber for 4 increasing levels of load. SEM images of composite under load 0,5 P_{max}.

Figure 6. The dissipated energy in the function of number of cycles for PA 6 with 50% glass fiber for 3 increasing levels of load.

Figure 7. The elongation in the function of number of cycles for PA 6 with 25% glass fiber for 4 increasing levels of load.

Figure 8. The elongation in the function of number of cycles for PA 6 with 50% glass fiber for 3 increasing levels of load.

In Fig. 9. The SEM images of fracture surface were shown. After 100 000 cycles of loading we can observe that some fibers were pulled out and spaces between the matrix and the fibers.

After 1 000 cycles of loading

After 100 000 cycles of loading

Figure 9. The SEM images of PA6 composite filled with 25% of glass fibre.

CONCLUSION

In the tested composites we can observe changes of mechanical properties and structure under cyclic loading. For the higher content of glass fibre (50%) in composite, number of cycles which causes fatigue is lower with reference to level of loading (0,1-0,55 P_{max}). Along with raising the value of load, we can observe increase of strain and energy of dissipation, especially up to 1 000 cycles of load. The modulus of elasticity decreased under cyclic loading of about 15% in comparison to the modulus obtained in the static test. For the level of load corresponding to a half value of the tensile strength of composites, number of cycles causing the fracture was 88 000 for PA 6 with 25% glass fibre and 10 000 for PA 6 with 50% glass fibre. It indicates that relative fatigue strength is much lower for the composite with higher fibre content.

For the high level of load and fracture of composite after small number of cycles (about 10 000), the dominate mechanism of fracture is cracking of matrix and fibres. For lower levels of loads and high number of cycles we can additionally observe the effect of disconnection between matrix and fibres. The character of fracture changed from brittle (after about 1 000 cycles of load) to ductile after fatigue fracture.

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